

GREEN PLANT ROLLER IN ENVIRONMENTAL MANAGEMENT

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Annotation: as a result of deforestation, we can be exposed to short-term or long-term risks. Currently, deforestation is one of the main causes of erosion of our soils. The removal of trees and shrubs affects the erosive forces of wind and water on the soil.

Base words: tree, nature, plant, oxygen, photosynthesis, water, erosion, industrial enterprise, vehicles, forest, soil, carbon dioxide, harort, light.

As we deal with our daily life, we consider many of the benefits of trees to be simple. Trees are not only beauty, they also play a decisive role in preserving life on Earth. They provide us with oxygen, fresh air, food, medicine and are also a habitat for wild animals.

Trees also play a decisive role in climate regulation, soil erosion prevention and Biodiversity Conservation. Because forests help slow down the rate of climate change by removing and storing carbon dioxide from the atmosphere.

The most favorable environment for the human organism is the presence of an air temperature of +20 +22 degrees, equal to 40-60 percent of its humidity, as well as the enrichment of atmospheric air with ions. The urbanization process is causing severe pollution of atmospheric air. Dirty gases from cars, waste from industrial enterprises have exceeded the amounts of harmful dust in the air. It is industrial enterprises and vehicles that are also the largest consumers of oxygen. These means disrupt the optimal composition of the air, causing a sharp increase in temperature in it.

The only means that naturally cleanses the air are Green Groves. In the process of photosynthesis, the oxygen secreted by one hectare of Green Wood will be enough for 200 people to breathe freely. However, in this process, the plant absorbs up to 8 kg of uglekislotu gas every hour. In other words, 50 sq.m per person so that the urban air is maintained in the optimal amount. meters should be a Green Grove. At the same time, green trees are of great importance in lowering the radiation temperature in cities. Air humidity is also 4-7% higher in the dry season of the year than in the open area around trees, and much lower in the sernam seasons because of the increased transpiration in the leaves due to heat, the leaves absorb it when the humidity in the air is high.

Green Groves reduce the wind speed through which they pass by 3 times. The higher their descending coefficient as the wind intensifies. This prevents dust from spreading around the area. Most of the populated destinations in Uzbekistan have a high amount of dust in the air during the summer months. In this, along with other natural factors, an increase in industrial enterprises, a sharp increase in the number of cars, as well as harmful gases contained in atmospheric air and is causing the amount of waste to go far beyond the norm. When the requirements for greening are fully met, it is possible to clean the air from dust as well as possible using it. When building Green Groves for sanitary purposes, it is necessary to take into account the wind regime of the area and its character, the amount of waste being thrown into the atmosphere, the height above ground level, the chemical and physical composition.

When planting trees, tree species with a large horn-stem, with hanging leaves (all types of oak, birch, Mulberry, Catalpa, resin, black walnut, white poplar, maple, Jayda) catch and swallow dust well. They even have the ability to absorb and process harmful chemical compounds, especially hydrocarbons. In winters with little snow, and in early spring, also populated destinations, dust levels are high. This task is performed by dragonflies at this time when the leaves have dropped their leaf.

In order for Green Groves to fully fulfill its sanitary and hygienic function, it is necessary to establish masses of sufficient size, as well as to create plants based on natural requirements for the environment.

When placing trees, their ecological and biological peculiarities: the demand for light, soil and moisture, the interaction of trees with each other in space and time should be taken into account. The important thing is that the trees are not dense among themselves, otherwise the husk of oxygen excretion will subside. Only when there is enough light does the process of photosynthesis in the plant accelerate and, as a result, absorbs harmful gases well and secretes a lot of oxygen. When planting trees, the distance between them should not be less than 5-6 meters. According to research, 22 trees are needed to meet a person's oxygen needs in one day. As a result of deforestation, we can be exposed to short-term or long-term risks.

Forests and trees regulate temperatures throughout urban and rural landscapes. This reduces the amount of energy and carbon needed to cool the interior spaces. Many harmful pollutants in the air are associated with climate change, and healthy forests remove them from the air.

This will help clear the atmosphere and control the elevated temperature. They prevent erosion by reducing the impact of rain on the soil surface and absorbing water and preventing it from flowing directly and removing the top layer. Forests also act as a water filter, collecting and storing water and filling underground aquifers. Tropical mountain forests are particularly important for water bodies-many medicines and pharmaceutical preparations have been found in Forest-specific plants. The United Nations Food and rural hooligan Organization estimates that while forests originally occupied about 45 percent of the land area on Earth, forests now account for only 31 percent. According to the World Wide Fund for nature, forests are disappearing every year at a speed of 46-58 million square meters, which is equivalent to 36 football fields per minute. Lack of green space and air pollution are also causing major environmental problems in Uzbekistan. Therefore, deforestation in Uzbekistan affects not only biodiversity in forests, but also many fragile ecosystems such as river basins. In addition, the Tashkent region and Tashkent City face extreme air pollution, which also leads to ecosystem degradation through water and soil acidification. A number of measures are being implemented in order to eliminate these cases. In particular, the

decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 30, 2019 approved the “concept of Environmental Protection of the Republic of Uzbekistan’ for the period up to 2030. The concept places particular emphasis on reducing desertification and degradation levels of land, and restoring the quality and productivity of land areas. As part of the implementation of the decision of the head of state signed on October 6, 2020 “on approval of the concept of development of the forestry system in the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030” during 2021, measures to prevent desertification, fight erosion, reforestation and increase protection forests were carried out on the lands of the Forest Foundation in total Including, in the dry region of the Aral Sea, these activities were carried out in 458 thousand hectares, in the regions of Khorezm, Bukhara and Navoi regions, which are part of the Aral Sea region, in 148.5 thousand hectares. Also, on a total of 9.6 thousand hectares in the mountain and mountain areas of the Forest Foundation, plantations of Walnut fruit trees were organized. The practice of cultivating saxifrage and other desert plants has been established in preventing land conversion to desert. According to experts and scientists in the field, sand migration under the influence of wind in the 2-year-old saxaulzor, built on the territory of the Aral Sea, is completely stopped by 20 percent, in the 5-year-old saxaulzor by 80 percent, and in the 7-year-old saxaulzor by 7 percent. As a result, the climate in the insular region becomes temperate, the airlift of sand-dust decreases. For a person to live, the stability of the socio-economic environment is ensured. In addition on April 16, 2018, the law “on the Forest’ was adopted in a new revision. It has been established that the purpose of adopting a new revision of this law is to regulate relations in the field of forest protection, protection, reproduction, reproduction, restoration, increasing their productivity and their use.

The law on the forest clearly defines a number of issues. Including Forest Fund lands as forest-covered lands, as well as lands not covered by forest, but granted for forestry needs, were recognized as Forest Fund lands. There are also many activities under the green space project. According to the concept of development of the forestry

system in the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030, the area of Forest Foundation land is set to be 14 million hectares, of which forest-covered land is 6 million hectares.

Conclusion. Forests and Groves in Uzbekistan are of great importance for the environment, economy and people of the country. The protection of forests, groves and their sustainable management are decisive in ensuring a healthy environment, sustainable development and the well-being of current and future generations.

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